

AN OPTIMIZATION APPROACH FOR EFFECTIVE INTERSECTION CONTROL IN VANET BASED TRAFFIC SIGNAL CONTROLLER

Seelam Sai Satyanarayana Reddy

Post-Doctoral Fellow, California Public University, Delaware,
United States of America

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Abstract:

In present scenario, several countries making use of the traffic signaling without taken into account of the emergency vehicles like the medical emergency vehicle, fire and service vehicles, police patrols and so on, which leads to the elevation of waiting time in the traffic that causes severe damage to the assets and lives. One of the major aspect in the emergency vehicle management is the enhanced number of vehicles in the lane elevates the response time of the vehicle, thus automatically the waiting time in the traffic elevates. Thus, this research introduces an optimization based TSC for optimal controlling.

Key Words: VANET system Model, RSU, Peuco Trick Optimization, Mathematical Modeling

1. Introduction:

For the safer journey, the traffic signal at the intersection of the road is essential and guarantees the safe driving. This thesis chapter introduces an efficient technique for the traffic signal controlling using the newly devised Peuco- trick optimization algorithm. The newly developed optimization algorithm for controlling the traffic signal by considering the priority of the vehicle and several other factors is designed by integrating the collaborative behavior of the Peuco in hunting along with the communal interaction of the trickster to elevate the accuracy of signal controlling. For the evaluation of the optimal routing technique, the Vehicular Ad hoc Network (VANET) architecture is considered.

1.1 VANET system Model

With the increase in population, the vehicle usage become higher and hence, the congestion in the road elevates and the chances of clashes become higher. Thus, there is a need for the automatic traffic signal controlling technique to maintain the traffic flow by considering the emergency condition of the vehicle. Hence, this thesis chapter introduces an efficient traffic signal controlling optimally using the optimization algorithm by considering the VANET architecture. The VANET system model representing the traffic control at the intersection is illustrated in Figure 3.1. Here, the components such as road side unit (RSU), vehicles, users, traffic signal controller (TSC).

Figure 1.1: System Model

Transmission Link:

Here, for the proposed traffic signal controlling the dedicated short range communication link (DSRC) is utilized for the information sharing in the network.

RSU:

The range of the VANET is extended by utilizing the RSUs and is placed anywhere with the router. It is utilized for the data gathering form the vehicle and transmits to the server for further processing.

Vehicles:

The vehicles in the VANET communicate each other for the information sharing and it may be of vehicle-to-vehicle communication, vehicle to infrastructure and vehicle to pedestrian communications. The information sharing is employed through the installation of the GPS in the vehicles.

Traffic Signal Controller:

The traffic signal controller is tuned optimally using the proposed Peuco-trick optimization algorithm by considering several factors of the vehicles such as priority, acceleration, jitter and so on to manage the traffic effectively. Here, the ON or OFF of the traffic signal at the intersection is performed based on the solution encoding.

1.2 Data Collection:

The necessary information for the optimal control of the traffic signal to control the traffic at the intersection is gathered through the RSU. With the help of the GPS in the vehicles that are registered in the VANET, all the relevant information for the processing will be gathered.

1.2.1 Parameter Evaluation:

The parameters utilized in the proposed work to control the traffic light signaling are distance, velocity, acceleration, jitter, priority and historic importance.

Distance to Travelled (Z1):

The distance to travel by the vehicle to reach the destination in the VANET is extracted and is formulated as,

$$Z1 = Dist_{total} - Dist_{travelled} \tag{1.1}$$

Where, the travelled distance is notated as $Dist_{travelled}$, and the total distance of the vehicle from the source to destination is demonstrated as $Dist_{total}$.

Velocity (Z2):

At the particular time, the distance covered by the vehicle is measured to evaluate the vehicle's velocity and is formulated as,

$$Z2 = \frac{Dist_{travelled}}{n} \tag{1.2}$$

Where, n refers to the time taken.

Acceleration (Z3):

The change in speed of the vehicle is evaluated through the acceleration measure and is expressed as,

$$Z3 = \frac{Velocity\ variation}{n} \tag{1.3}$$

Jitter (Z4):

While communication through the VANET, the delay may occurs due to the congestion and is referred as jitter, which affects the performance of the system. The jitter in the proposed method is evaluated through the formula,

$$Z4 = \sum_{i=1}^W \exp \left[\eta \frac{Z3_{n+1} - Z3_n}{Z3_{th}} \right] \tag{1.4}$$

Where, the coefficient of adjustment is represented as η , $Z3_{th}$, refers to the acceleration threshold, $Z3_{n+1}$ refers to the vehicle's acceleration at $n + 1$ and the $Z3_n$ refers to the vehicle's acceleration at n .

Priority (Z5):

The priority is evaluated to identify the vehicles in emergency, which is measured by assigning weights to the vehicles in the VANET. The vehicles in the VANET are categorized into three basic priorities by considering the velocity and emergency condition. Here, for the medical emergency vehicles are considered as the highest priority vehicles and assigned weights for it is W_1 , then the second priority is assigned for the vehicle with high speed and is demonstrated as W_2 and all the remaining vehicles are considered with third priority and is notated as W_3 .

Historic Information (Z6):

The historic importance measure is evaluated to depict the present condition of the traffic signal, in which the ON condition of the signal is demonstrated as 1 and the OFF condition is demonstrated as 0. The evaluation of the historic information is essential for the enhancement of the traffic flow in the network.

Fusing of Attributes:

The above mentioned six attributes taken out from the input data is not fused together to form the vector of attributes and is represented as in equation (5). Thus, the collected attributes are utilized for the traffic signal control optimally at the intersection using the proposed Peuco trick optimization.

$$Z = \{Z1, Z2, Z3, Z4, Z5, Z6\} \tag{1.5}$$

Where, Z refers to the combined features.

1.4 Methodology for controlling the traffic signal at the intersection optimally Using Proposed Peuco Trick Optimization Algorithm:

The block diagram representing the proposed traffic signal controlling at the intersection is depicted in Figure 3.2. Here, initially, the information concerning the parameters of the vehicle is obtained through the RSU and from which the essential attributes are taken out from the information shared by the vehicle. The attributes such as the information of historic signaling control, acceleration, velocity, distance, priority and the jitter are extracted for the optimal signal controlling. In the proposed method, an optimization algorithm named, Peuco-Trick optimization is proposed to optimal controlling of traffic signal at the intersection to manage the traffic flow. The proposed Peuco-Trick optimization is designed by hybridizing the hunting behavior of the Peuco and the communal behavior of the trickster to obtain the best solution by exploring and exploiting the selected attributes to optimally control the traffic signal with more accuracy.

Figure 1.2: Proposed Traffic Signal Controlling

2. Solution Encoding:

The traffic signal ON/OFF control (TSC) to manage the traffic flow at the intersection is employed by the proposed Peuco Trick optimization. For this, let us assume there are 10 traffic signals in the VANET and they are controlled optimally through the objection function expressed in the equation (3.6) and the solution encoding is depicted in Figure 3.3 respectively. Let, the solution’s dimension may be referred as [1x10] with ν solutions. From this ν solutions, the optimal solution for controlling the traffic signal is evaluated using the proposed Peuco Trick optimization algorithm.

$$OF = n1[Zi] + n2[Z2] + n3[Z3] + n4[Z4] + n5[Z5] + n6[Z6] \tag{1.6}$$

Where, OF refers to the objection function, and $n1, n2, n3, n4, n5$ and $n6$ are the constant, in which $n1 + n2 + n3 + n4 + n5 + n6 = 1$.

Figure 1.3: Solution Encoding

2.1 Measure of Fitness:

The proposed method evaluates the fitness for optimal controlling of the traffic signal by considering the targeted output to enhance the accuracy of controlling and is evaluated as,

$$FM = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k (U^k - \hat{U}^k)^2 \tag{1.7}$$

Where, the total population is demonstrated as k , the target and the estimated output is notated as \hat{U}^k and U^k respectively and the fitness is depicted as FM .

2.2 Proposed Peuco Trick Optimization for Traffic Signal Controlling:

The proposed Peuco trick optimization for the controlling of the intersection for the traffic signal control is designed by hybridizing the collaborative behavior of the Peuco in hunting [106] along with the communal interaction of the trickster [107] to escape from Peuco while attacking. The hybridization of the

characteristic behavior of the Peuco and the trickster helps to balance the diversification and the intensification phase to obtain the global best solution in solving the optimal traffic signal control in the intersection of the road.

Mathematical Modeling:

The mathematical modeling of the proposed Peuco trick optimization algorithm for controlling the traffic signal in the VANET by considering the attributes such as the historical importance, priority, acceleration, jitter, velocity, and the distance to travel is detailed here. The proposed Peuco trick optimization algorithm evaluates the above mentioned attributes and optimally controls the traffic signal.

The proposed Peuco trick optimization algorithm follows three phases for the optimal signal controlling the intersection like diversification, switching, and intensification phase. In the first phase, the attributes extracted from the VANET is explored in-depth and then the best quality features are analyzed within the explored feature to find the best solution. The transition that takes place between the exploring and the exploiting phase is considered the switching phase.

$$A(i + 1) = \begin{cases} A_p(i) - a_1 |A_p(i) - 2a_2 A(i)| & s \geq 0.5 \\ [A_c(i) - A_u(i)] - a_3 [B + a_4(D - B)] & s < 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (1.8)$$

Here, the population of the Peuco is considered and each individual in the population refers to the solution for controlling the traffic signal. The best solution identified is considered the best solution to control the traffic signal to manage the traffic in VANET.

Diversification Phase: In this phase, the Peuco monitors using the powerful eyes to identify the prey for a long waiting time, it may even for several hours. After detecting the prey it utilizes two different strategies to capture the prey. In the first strategy, it moves close to the family and captures them, for this the condition $s \geq 0.5$ is considered. In the second strategy, it perches on the tall tree and attacks the prey, the condition utilized for this strategy is $s < 0.5$. Then, the position of the Peuco is updated as,

Where, The current location of the Peuco based on the average is notated as A_u , the present location of the Peuco is notated as A_i , and the present position of the prey is notated as $A_c(i)$, in which i refers to the iteration, and the position of the Peuco is referred as $A(i + 1)$. The random numbers in the interval $[0,1]$ are notated as $a_4, a_3, a_2,$ and a_1 respectively. Then, the lower bound limit and the upper bound limit of the search space are referred as B and D respectively. The position based on the average location of the Peuco is formulated as,

$$A_u(i) = \frac{1}{E} \sum_{i=1}^E A_i(i) \quad (1.9)$$

Where, the Peuco's location is denoted as $A_i(i)$, the Peuco's total number is denoted as E .

Switching Phase:

After exploring the target region, which means exploring the attributes, the Peuco exploits deeply inside the attributes. In this, phase, the prey tries to escape from the Peuco with maximum energy and it is formulated as,

$$G = 2G_0 \left(1 - \frac{i}{I} \right) \quad (1.10)$$

Where, the prey's energy utilized for escaping from the Peuco's attack is referred as G , I notates the maximal iteration number and the random number that changes between $[-1, 1]$ for each iteration is referred as G_0 . Here, when $|G| \geq 1$, Peuco diversifies more and when $|G| < 1$ it intensifies more.

Intensification Phase:

In this phase, the optimal best solution is obtained. Here, the prey tries to escape from the Peuco and four different strategies are utilized to find the best solution to tune the traffic signal. Let the parameter r depicts the chance of the prey either escaping or not. When the condition $q < 0.5$ is there is a chance to escape else, there is no chance to escape from the Peuco.

Strategy 1:

The condition $|G \geq 1|$ and $q \geq 0.5$ needs to be satisfied. In this, strategy, the prey has the maximum energy and escape from the Peuco by jumping randomly in the search space and is formulated as,

$$A(i + 1) = \Delta A(i) - G |FA_c(i) - A(i)| \quad (1.11)$$

$$\Delta A(i) = A_c(i) - A(i) \tag{1.12}$$

$$F = 2(1 - a_5) \tag{1.13}$$

Where, the prey's strength while jumping randomly to escape from the Peuco is notated as F and the random number ranges between $[0,1]$ is referred as a_5 .

Strategy 2:

The condition for this strategy is $q \geq 0.5$ and $|G| < 0.5$. Here, in this strategy, the energy of the prey is lower and so it cannot able to escape from the attacker and hence the communal behavior of the trickster is utilized to escape the prey from the Peuco and is formulated as,

$$A(i+1) = A_c(i) - G|\Delta A(i)| \tag{1.14}$$

The equation can be rewritten as,

$$A_c(i) = A(i+1) + G|\Delta A(i)| \tag{1.15}$$

The update equation of the trickster based on the communal behavior is formulated as,

$$A_c(i+1) = A(i) + y_1 R_1 + y_2 R_2 \tag{1.16}$$

Where, the random number ranges between the $[0,1]$ in the normal distribution is referred as y_1 and y_2 respectively. In addition, R_1 refers to the random number that can be formulated as,

$$R_1 = \begin{cases} V_{(N+1)/2, g}^i & \text{if } N \text{ is odd} \\ V_{N/2, g}^i + V_{(N/2+1), g}^i & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{1.17}$$

Where, R_1 refers to the escaping position of the prey based on the communal behavior of the trickster from the Peuco and R_2 is the best location of the prey while escaping from the attacker. Then, the final update equation of the prey can be expressed as,

$$A_c(i+1) - y_1 R_1 - y_2 R_2 = A(i+1) + G|\Delta A(i)| \tag{1.18}$$

Then, the final update equation of the Peuco can be expressed as,

$$A(i+1) = [A_c(i+1) - y_1 R_1 - y_2 R_2] - G|\Delta A(i)| \tag{1.19}$$

Strategy 3:

The condition for this strategy is $q < 0.5$ and $|G| \geq 0.5$. Here, the leapfrog movement is utilized by the Peuco to capture the prey and is formulated as in equation (3.20). The Peuco, in this strategy, makes the diving movement to capture the prey.

$$H = A_c(i) - G|FA_c(i) - A(i)| \tag{1.20}$$

Where, the next move of the Peuco is notated as H . Then, the movement based on the irregular motion is utilized by the Peuco to capture the prey and is formulated as,

$$J = H + K \times L(M) \tag{1.21}$$

Where, the levy flight of the Peuco to attack the prey is notated as L and the dimension of the problem is referred as M , and the random vector with the dimension $[1 \times M]$ is denoted as K . The levy flight movement is expressed as,

$$L(e) = 0.01 \times \frac{r \times \alpha}{(w)^{1/\sigma}} \tag{1.22}$$

where, $\alpha = \left[\frac{\gamma(1+\sigma) \times \sin\left(\frac{\pi\sigma}{2}\right)}{\gamma\left(\frac{1+\sigma}{2}\right) \times \sigma \times 2^{\left(\frac{\sigma-1}{2}\right)}} \right]^{1/\sigma}$ (1.23)

Let the default constant σ is assigned as 1.5 and the random value ranges between [0,1] is notated as r and w . The final update solution of the Peuco for the strategy 3 is expressed as,

$$A(i+1) = \begin{cases} H & \text{if } F(H) < F(A(i)) \\ J & \text{if } F(J) < F(A(i)) \end{cases} \quad (1.24)$$

Strategy 4:

The condition $|G| < 0.5$ and $q < 0.5$ needs to be satisfied, in which the prey has no energy to escape and it is caught by the Peuco and the position is updated as,

$$A(i+1) = \begin{cases} H & \text{if } F(H) < F(A(i)) \\ J & \text{if } F(J) < F(A(i)) \end{cases} \quad (1.25)$$

$$H = A_c(i) - G|FA_c(i) - A_u(i)| \quad (1.26)$$

$$J = H + K \times L(M) \quad (1.27)$$

Termination:

The above mentioned process continues for the maximum number of iterations fixed or until the attainment of the global best solution to control the traffic signal optimally.

Algorithm 2.1: Pseudo-code for the proposed Peuco Trick optimization algorithm

Pseudo-code for proposed Peuco Trick optimization algorithm	
1	Input: Initialize the population size, maximum iteration number
2	Output: Optimal best solution to tune traffic signal control
3	While (i<I)
4	Evaluate the fitness for all the Peuco in search space
5	Set the location of the prey
6	for
7	{
8	Update G_0
9	Update G
10	If ($ G \geq 1$)
11	Update the position using equation (3.8)
12	If ($ G < 1$)
13	If ($ G \geq 1$ and $q \geq 0.5$)
14	Update the position using the equation (3.11)
15	Else if ($q \geq 0.5$ and $ G < 0.5$)
16	Update the position using the equation (3.19)
17	Else if ($q < 0.5$ and $ G \geq 0.5$)
18	Update the position using the equation (3.24)
19	Else if ($ G < 0.5$ and $q < 0.5$)
20	Update the position using the equation (3.25)
21	End for
22	Return the best solution
23	i=i++
24	stop

3. Result and Discussion:

The proposed Peuco trick optimization for the optimal traffic signal controlling is implemented using MATLAB with Windows 10 OS and 8GB RAM. The performance of the method is analyzed using Average traffic density (min), Average Speed (m/s), Distance (m), and Travel Time (s).

Performance Metrics:

The definition and formulation of the performance metrics are elaborated here,

Average Traffic Density (Min):

The traffic flow rate and the travel speed of the vehicles in the lane are utilized and is formulated as,

$$ATD = \frac{(flow\ rate)_i}{Average\ Travel\ Speed} \tag{1.28}$$

Where, the average traffic density is notated as ATD , and $(flow\ rate)_i$ refers to the vehicle flow at time i .

Average Speed (m/s):

Average speed of the vehicle is estimated by considering the total distance travelled by the vehicle and time and is formulated as,

$$AS = \frac{Total\ distance}{Total\ Time} \tag{1.29}$$

Where, the average speed is notated as AS .

Distance (m): The distance is evaluated based on time and speed and is formulated as,

$$Dis = speed \times time \tag{1.30}$$

Where, the distance is notated as Dis .

Travel Time (s): The time is evaluated by considering the distance and speed and is formulated as,

$$TT = \frac{Dis}{Time} \tag{1.31}$$

Where, the travel time is notated as TT .

Figure 1.4 represents the Distance estimation. The Distance acquired at one vehicle is 82.9037, 85.6730, 76.2940, 86.7442, and 72.7803 respectively by the proposed Peuco Trick based TSC corresponding to 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 solutions, which is 74.2233, 71.4795, 80.1128, 71.0775, and 71.0775 for 200 vehicles.

Figure 1.4: Analysis using Distance with 200 vehicles

Figure 1.5 represents the Travel Time estimation. The Travel Time acquired with one vehicle is 44.6592, 30.7143, 65.3571, 37.9062, and 30.7143 respectively by the proposed Peuco Trick based TSC corresponding to 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 solutions, which 55.1879, 58.5784, 64.8284, 42.1569, and 42.1569 for 200 vehicles.

Figure 1.5: Analysis using Travel Time with 200 vehicles

4. Summary:

This paper explains detailed the traffic light signal controller at the intersection using the proposed Peuco Trick optimization algorithm. The information of the vehicle like distance to travel, velocity, acceleration, jitter, priority and historic information are gathered by the RSU and using the Peuco trick optimization, the optimal traffic signal controlling is employed. The performance of the proposed method by varying the vehicle numbers depicts the scalability of the method.

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